

FLIGHT FOLDER

Flight No.	B493		
Date:	04 DEC 2009		
Take Off:	11:24:08Z	Z	Z
Landing:	16:35:56Z	Z	Z
Flight Time:	2h 59m 43s	h m s	h m s

Campaign: QUEFA/CAP

Operating Area: London M25 orbits and Weybourne

POB	Position	Name	Institute
1	Captain	Alan Roberts	Directflight
2	Co	Ian Ramsay-Rae	Directflight
3	CCM	Dawn Quinn	Directflight
4	Mission Scientist /WAS	Jim Hopkins	York
5	Flight Manager	Alan Woolley	FAAM
6	Core Chemistry / WAS 2	Axel Wellpot	FAAM
7	AMS	Will Morgan	Manchester
8	Cloud Physics / Neph / CCN	Jamie Trembath	FAAM
9	Familiarisation	Guy Gratton	FAAM
10	Pilot 3	Luc Lathouwers	Directflight
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	Log Sheet included
Y	Flight Folder Front Page
Y	Flight Summary
Y	Met Office 0600 UTC Actual Surface analysis (ASXX) chart
Y	Track Plot (GIN or GPS)
	DFLFliteStar planned track
Y	Brief
Y	Mission Scientist 1's logs
	Mission Scientist 2's logs
	De-brief
	ViRC chat log
	Flight Manager's Instrument Status log
Y	Flight Manager's Faults/Incidents log
	Pre-flight log
	Core Chemistry / NOx / TDLAS
Y	Cloud Physics In Flight
	Cloud Physics Processing
	AVAPS
	PSAP log
	Filters
	Printed Plots
	Screengrabs
	Planning charts or plots
	Images Emailed To BAe146 In Flight

Revision	Date	Author	Comments
r0	2009-11-05	Alan Woolley	Initial version
R1			
r2			

Flights around London to quantify the emissions of Volatile organic compounds and other trace gases from the city. Two consecutive circuits around the city at fixed altitude within the boundary layer.

Missed approaches at Northolt airport will give us a profile through the atmosphere and verify the position of the boundary layer. These will be performed at the start and end of each flight to check whether it has altered in this time.

WAS canisters should be filled in “fast-fill” mode. Given the relatively large number of WAS canisters on board we should aim to get an even spacing between samples (around one every 1 – 1.5 minutes) REGARDLESS of whether CO is calibrating.

CO calibrations should be performed once during the circuits.

Figure 1: Position of Waypoints during circuits around London and Norwich.

London sortie: F – A – B – C – D – E – F – A – B – C – D – E

Norwich sortie: G – H – I – J – K – L – G – H – I – J – K – L – G

Sortie 1: London (approximately 3 hours)

#	approx time	approx altitude	detail
(1)	TBD	take off	Take off and ascend to transit level - preferably FL100, but the pilots will decide
(2)		transit altitude	transit to operating area - Fill some WAS canisters (5) at this level.
(3)		descend	Descend into Northolt airport and perform a missed approach
(4)		ascend	Ascend to 2300 ft. - Or minimum safe altitude
(5)		2300 ft	Perform two complete anti-clockwise circuits of the city at this level starting at point F (see figure 1). F – A – B – C – D – E – F – A – B – C – D – E. - fill the remaining WAS canisters equally spread around both circuits approximately every 90 s.
(6)		descend	Descend into Northolt airport and perform a missed approach
(7)		ascend	Ascend to above 2300 ft - to verify the boundary layer height has not changed during the flight
(8)		transit altitude	Transit to North Norfolk Coast for CAP flying, sortie details below

B493b – CAP 3

Mission Scientist: Jim Hopkins

Date: 4 December 2009

Outline schedule (All times local): T/O Landing To be decided

Location: North Norfolk Coast – over Weybourne Atmospheric Observatory (WAO)

Aim: To sample the boundary layer structure and composition around WAO.

Sortie Detail For location of way points see below.

1. (35 mins)
 - a) Transit from M25 and proceed towards LW
 - b) Straight and level run at 1300 ft from LW to LE
 - c) Straight and level run at 1300 ft from LS to ON

2. (30 mins)
 - a) Straight and level run at 1300 ft from OE to OW
 - b) Straight and level run at 800 ft from OW to OE
 - c) Straight and level run at 300 ft from OE to OW
 - d) Run from OW to OE starting at 100 ft and dipping to 50 ft just offshore of WAO

- 3 (20 mins)
 - a) Straight and level run at 2000 ft from OE to OW
 - b) Straight and level run at 2000 ft from ON to LS
 - c) Straight and level run at 2000 ft from LW to LE

- 4.1 (15 mins)
 - a) Straight and level run at 4000 ft from LS to ON

- 5.1
 - b) Straight and level run at 6000 ft from ON to LS

- 6 (20 mins)
 - a) Transit to Cranfield

Table 1. Way points around WAO

Way Points	Latitude	Longitude
WAO	52°57'02"N	1°07'19"E
OW (Ocean West)	53°01'00"N	0°57'00"E
OE (Ocean East)	52°57'30"N	1°22'00"E
ON (Ocean North)	53°03'30"N	1°10'00"E
LW (Land West)	52°57'00"N	0°54'30"E
LE (Land East)	52°53'30"N	1°19'30"E
LS (Land South)	52°48'30"N	1°04'00"E

Fill bottles on runs:

Table 2. Runs around WAO between the Way Points (WP)

Step	Run	Altitude ft asl	From WP	To WP
1	1.1	1300	LW	LE
1	1.2	1300	LS	ON
2	2.1	1300	OE	OW
2	2.2	800	OW	OE
2	2.3	300	OE	OW
2	2.4	100	OW	OE
3	3.1	2000	OE	OW
3	3.2	2000	ON	LS
3	3.3	2000	LW	LE
4	4.1	4000	LS	ON
5	5.1	6000	ON	LS

asxx 04/12/2009 12:00 UTC

Faults / Incidents Log

Flight No. B493

Date: 04 Dec 09

Instruments

1. Nevz TWC zeros okay but signal output always flatlines (at 0uA on control unit meter). DLU reading always 6346 DRSU.
- 2.

Aircraft

- 1.

Satcom

MPDS –

Satcom H –

Post Flight - Turb Probe Water Traps

1. Indicate Amount of Water: a) Nil b) 1-2 drops c) $\frac{1}{4}$ full or more d) Ice present
2. Emptied by:
3. Dried by:

FLIGHT SUMMARY

Flight No B493

Date:4/12/09

Project:CAP/QUEFA

Location:London M25 and Weybourne

Start End

Time Time Event Height (s) Hdg Comments

Time	Time	Event	Height (s)	Hdg	Comments
112408		T/O	0.48 kft	212	
113009	114042	Run 1	10.0 kft	273	
114052	114837	Profile 1	9.9 - 5.1 kft	266	
114254		Profile 1	8.0 kft	108	interrupt
114554		Profile 1	8.0 kft	104	
114942	115520	Profile 2	5.0 - 0.33 kft	207	
115841	132048	Run 2	2.5 - 2.4 kft	263	
120009		point F	2.4 kft	237	
120114		jw/nev	2.4 kft	236	zero
120615		point A	2.4 kft	152	
122207		mpds gone	2.4 kft	086	
122226		point C	2.4 kft	044	
122801		point D	2.4 kft	352	
123322		point e	2.4 kft	296	
123703		mpds gone	2.4 kft	274	
123856		mpds back	2.4 kft	272	
124408		point F	2.4 kft	234	
125039		point A	2.5 kft	147	
125816		point B	2.4 kft	116	
130443		mpds gone	2.4 kft	088	
130634		point C	2.5 kft	021	
130806		mpds back	2.5 kft	015	
131159		point D	2.4 kft	351	
132043		point E	2.5 kft	276	a bit late!
132106	132633	Profile 3	2.2 - 0.32 kft	276	
132217		mpds gone	2.2 kft	278	
132238		mpds back	2.2 kft	266	
133120	133341	Profile 4	2.6 - 4.6 kft	350	
133341	133758	Run 3	4.6 - 4.7 kft	348	
133803	134348	Profile 5	4.8 - 10.0 kft	029	
134535		mpds gone	10.0 kft	055	

Run Numberings Reset to fit with CAP Brief and ground synchronisation

134700	mpds back	10.0 kft	057
135614	135928 Profile 6	4.7 - 1.5 kft	296
135929	140434 Run 1.1	1.5 kft	101
140224	abeam	1.5 kft	101
140915	141349 Run 1.2	1.6 kft	001
141155	ovhd wao	1.6 kft	014
141740	142229 Run 2.1	1.6 - 1.5 kft	263
142033	abeam wao	1.6 kft	283
142230	142312 Profile 7	1.5 - 1.0 kft	286
142522	143031 Run 2.2	1.0 - 0.98 kft	103
143031	143133 Profile 7	0.98 - 0.51 kft	106
143257	p7 rename p8	0.71 kft	248
143332	143923 Run 2.3	0.55 - 0.49 kft	300
144301	144725 Run 2.4	0.28 - 0.35 kft	106 with 50ft dip
144502	@50ft reallyY!	0.23 kft	104
144725	145040 Profile 9	0.35 - 2.2 kft	102
145050	145955 Run 3.1	2.2 kft	276
150037	150458 Run 3.2	2.2 kft	174
150943	151338 Run 3.3	2.2 kft	088
151356	151609 Profile 10	2.3 - 4.2 kft	137
151810	152235 Run 4.1	4.2 kft	352
152235	152417 Profile 11	4.2 - 6.0 kft	013
152620	153117 Run 5.1	6.0 kft	200
155027	mpds failed	7.0 kft	240
160223	Land	0.51 kft	210